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Hydrogen

RHeaDHy: Refuelling Heavy Duty with very high flow Hydrogen

Introduction to RHeaDHy test matrix

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

RHeaDHy project aims to develop a high-flow refuelling line and its components to enable the construction of appropriate infrastructure for hydrogen heavy-duty vehicles. To achieve the project's goals, an extensive test campaign will be conducted. This note details the tests envisioned for RHeaDHy test campaign and offers the industry and public an opportunity to review the test campaigns outline. RHeaDHy consortium welcomes feedback on both the overall approach and the specific test details or test conditions.

The main goals of this test campaign are to:

- **Demonstrate high-flow refuelling** with the RHeaDHy equipment
- **Characterize the equipment** developed within the project
- **Ensure RHeaDHy KPI are met**
- **Map station performance**
- **Provide feedback on high-flow refuelling protocols** to the industry
- Provide **public access to test results** to support research and innovation
- **Support the hydrogen heavy-duty mobility industry**

In addition, developing a **safe technology** and refueling process is a key priority for the RHeaDHy project, and safety will remain a central focus throughout the test campaign.

To validate these objectives during the testing phase, a test matrix has been established. **The test matrix divides the test campaign into batches**, grouping tests by goal. The batches are:

- **Ramp-up**
- **KPI testing**
- **Protocol testing**
- **Partners' specific tests**
- **External partnerships**
- **Certification tests**
- **Optimization tests**
- **Other tests**

The batches are detailed in section 3.1 and an overview of the test matrix is provided in [Table I](#).

It is worth noting that some batches (mostly those of high priority) are already detailed in [ANNEX I – First version of test matrix](#) while others are not. This is intentional, as feedback from the first tests will be used to define the remaining ones more precisely. Moreover, the number of tests in each batch may be adjusted during the campaign.

RHeaDHy aims to promote transparency, foster innovation, and support scientific research and collaboration across the hydrogen mobility. To this end, some test data will be made publicly available (e.g through peer-reviewed papers or other publications). In addition, a report summarizing the main conclusions of RHeaDHy test campaign will be published at the end of the project.

I What is the RHeaDHy project?

RHeaDHy project aims to support the reduction of transportation emissions by enabling the development of hydrogen heavy-duty vehicles (HDV) refuelling infrastructure. In the wake of the PRHYDE project¹ which focused on developing high-flow refuelling protocols, RHeaDHy project objective is to develop a high-flow refuelling line and its components in order to test new high-flow refuelling protocols and enable the construction of suitable infrastructure for hydrogen HDV. More precisely, **RHeaDHy main goals are** the following:

- **Development of high-flow components and a high-flow refuelling line:** design and build valves, heat exchanger, flowmeter, cooling system and dispenser capable of fuelling 100 kg in 10 minutes, reaching a maximal flow of 300 g/s. The station should be reliable and have reasonable energy consumption.
- **Extensive testing of refuelling line:** test prototype dispensers with a test bench representative of a truck tank system with approximately 100 kg hydrogen capacity. Different high-flow refuelling protocols will be implemented and used during the extensive test campaign.
- **Facilitating fast deployment of the high-flow stations:** certify the developed components and ensure RHeaDHy dispenser meets the market needs and complies with existing and future standards; thanks to active participation of its members in standardization working groups, constitution of a project advisory board and active communication with the hydrogen mobility ecosystem.

RHeaDHy project began in early 2023 and involves nine partners: ENGIE Lab CRIGEN, HRS (Hydrogen Refuelling Solutions), ZBT (Zentrum für BrennstoffzellenTechnik), FORVIA (Faurecia), LAUDA, ALFA-LAVAL, EMERSON TESCO, EMERSON MICROMOTION, and BENKEI. The first half of the project focused on specifying the dispenser components and truck storage test system, designing the prototypes, building and testing the valves, heat-exchanger, flowmeter and cooling system, and finally assembling and building the dispenser. At the time of this publication, work on setting up the test station is ongoing, and the next steps will be to commission the developed refuelling line and to start the RHeaDHy test campaign.

More information on RHeaDHy project can be found on the website : www.rheadhy.eu and on previous public deliverable [D6.6 – Recommendations for standardization – M24](#). Contact information for each organisation is also available on the website. For general inquiries, please reach out to ENGIE (coordinator) and BENKEI.

¹ See www.prhyde.eu

2 Test campaign objectives

RHeaDHy dispenser and its components is planned to be tested on two sites: at ZBT (Germany) and HRS (France). Each site will have its own Truck Storage Test System (TSTS) made by Forvia, that will be used as a heavy-duty vehicle to conduct high-flow refuelling.

The **main objectives** of the RHeaDHy project test campaign are the following:

- **Conduct high-flow refuelling with RHeaDHy equipment:** prove such high-flow refuelling (between 120 and 300 g/s) are indeed achievable with the RHeaDHy setup.
- **Characterize the equipment developed in the project:** get data on their behaviour, check they meet the project specifications and are well suited to a high-flow station.
- **Check all the RHeaDHy KPI are met:** show that it is possible to fuel 100 kg of hydrogen in 10 minutes, to hold - 30°C precooling during a whole fuelling, to reach 300 g/s. 300 refuelling tests needs to be conducted.
- **Map the station performance:** get an overview of the behaviour and performance in all the representative operating conditions that can happen at future hydrogen refuelling stations.
- **Provide feedback on the high-flow refuelling protocols to the industry:** share results on the performance of various high-flow refuelling protocols that have not yet been tested at very high flowrate in real conditions.
- **Support the hydrogen heavy-duty mobility industry:** RHeaDHy is willing to partner with different actors, conduct tests with them and perform joined analysis on the results.

In addition, **safety is and will continue to be a main focus in RHeaDHy project.** Ensuring the safety of personnel, equipment and environment is the first priority, and ensuring the safety of the dispenser's design and automation under all operating conditions is also a key objective of the project, on top of other performance objectives.

In order to be able to validate all these objectives during the testing phase while respecting time and budget constraints, a test matrix was established and is detailed in next part.

3 Test plan

3.1 Introduction to test plan and test batches

To achieve all goals set for the test campaign as well as structuring the vast total number of tests, the refuelling tests to conduct have been organized in eight different batches, as listed below. The abbreviations for the batches are indicated in brackets and will be later on referred to find tests and test results through a dedicated ID for each individual test.

- **Ramp-up (RAM):**
This batch will take place just after commissioning and before conducting the first full high performance refuelling events. To redundantly assure all developed components withstand the very high-flow (300 g/s) as expected, the flow during the tests is progressively increased. This batch includes 10 tests and will be the first batch to be done.
- **KPI testing (KPI):**
This batch will allow to prove RHeaDHy KPI are met. It includes 15 tests, and is of high priority. Both 10 mm nozzle/receptacle combination and an 8 mm version will be tested. For the rest of the campaign, most tests will use the 8 mm nozzle/receptacle combination.
- **Protocol testing (PRO):**
This batch focuses on high-flow protocol testing. It contains 85 tests and is divided into three sub-batches:
 - SAEJ2601-5 basic testing (PRO-SAE):
This sub-batch consists in testing SAE J2601-5 protocol in various ambient and operating conditions to check that the refuelling behaviour is safe, and performant as expected.
 - SAEJ2601-5 options testing (PRO-SAO):
This sub-batch focuses on testing optional and new features of SAE J2601-5, as PRR Taper, K0 method or volume measurement method.
 - PRHYDE testing (PRO-PRH):
This sub-batch aims to test PRHYDE refuelling protocols with the RHeaDHy setup, focusing on the two protocols variants Tgas initial+ and Tgasthrottle.
- **RHeaDHy partner specific tests (PAR):**
This batch allows each RHeaDHy consortium member to test and qualify their product both under real-world conditions and in specific scenarios that may offer particularly valuable insights. This will be a batch of 34 dedicated tests, with five sub-batches for the respective component developers:
 - EMERSON-TESCOM specific tests (PAR-EMT)
 - EMERSON-MICROMOTION specific tests (PAR-EMM)
 - FORVIA specific tests (PAR-FOR)
 - ALFA LAVAL specific tests (PAR-ALF)
 - LAUDA specific tests (PAR-LAU)
- **External partnerships (EXT):**
RHeaDHy offers unique opportunities and access to state of the art refuelling technology and testing capabilities. This batch opens up the test campaign for partners outside of the original project consortium. The objective is to use the unique infrastructure to conduct tests in partnership with other main players of the hydrogen mobility industry (i.e. manufacturers of components such as nozzle, hose, receptacle or tank systems / vehicles, research institutions for joined tests and inter-institute comparison, etc.). Up to 97 tests are dedicated for this purpose, with a first partnership already agreed to and communicated:
 - Twin-nozzle testing (EXT-TWN)
This sub-batch will include tests utilising the twin-nozzle protocol approach and a tank system provided by TOYOTA.
 - External partner 2 to N (EXT-EP2 ... EXT-EPN):

These sub-batches are placeholders for potential partnerships. Some of them are already well engaged while other opportunities still need to be explored. In particular, it is likely different hardware configurations (nozzle, receptacle, hose) by different manufacturers will be tested.

- **Certification tests (CER),**
This batch allows to do specific tests needed for components to get relevant certification for their market use. For the moment, a sub-batch is envisioned to do OIML R139 specific tests for the flowmeter (CER-FLM): 9 tests are foreseen for this specific purpose for now.
- **Optimization tests (OPT):**
This batch comes later in the test campaign and shall allow to conduct tests with the goal of optimising station refuelling performance. Around 25 tests are currently envisioned, with three sub-batches that will probably evolve depending on the test campaigns first results. Specific sub-batches foreseen are covering topics such as:
 - o Cost vs speed study and optimization (OPT-COS)
 - Refuelling protocol optimization (OPT-PRT)
 - o Cascade arrangement and use optimization (OPT-CAS)
- **Other tests (OTH):**
This batch groups other tests of interest. Around 25 tests are currently dedicated to it, and would allow to stretch RHeaDHy test results to a broader range of applications. For the moment, three sub-batches are envisioned but subject to change depending of the test campaigns first results any other developments over the course of the campaign:
 - o Other type of vehicles testing (buseon trailers, ...) (OTH-VEH)
 - o Other station configurations testing (OTH-STA)
 - o Simulation validation specific tests (OTH-SIM)

An overview of the test matrix is given in [Table 1](#).

3.2 Introduction to test matrix structure

As explained in 3.1 the test matrix is structured into batches, and each batch contains a given number of individual tests. The test matrix itself contains a number of different variables and parameters to characterise each individual test. These define the key factors and also the purpose of the test. Main parameters that are subject to change for some tests are:

- **Tank system**, Forvia TSTS as a default or other tank system, and the configuration of the tank system (i.e. usage of only some of the system tanks)
- **Initial pressure**
- **Refuelling protocol** (SAE J2601-5, PRHYDE, Manual ramp, etc.), and options of the refuelling protocol if any
- **Precooling temperature** targeted (e.g. T30)
- **Ambient temperature:** range to target for the test
- **Initial gas and tank temperature**, e.g. close to the ambient, significantly hotter or significantly colder
- **Stop criteria**, according to protocol or to other conditions

Detailed test matrix is given in ANNEX I – First version of test matrix. The batches that are considered to be of the highest priority are already very detailed, as they will be conducted as soon as possible. The ones with a lower priority are not detailed in the same level, as they will be subject to change depending on the initial test results and also possible external partnerships. Additionally, collecting results from the high-priority batches will allow to refine the numerical models used for the simulations models in order to get more accurate control parameters, identify other possibly interesting conditions to investigate more, or to allow to repeat tests. The large number of tests to be conducted within the RHeaDHy test campaign allows for a flexible and dynamic

approach to ensure that both the projects main goals as well as new findings can be sufficiently addressed. It also means that **the number of tests in each batch listed above might be subject to change. In particular, the last batches (OPT and OTH) will be served as buffer and provide flexibility to accommodate unforeseen failures or developments.** The tests within these batches are not crucial to meet RHeaDHy main goals, but would serve a broader interest for the industry. Similarly, the number of external partner tests (EXT) will depend on the final partnerships contractually agreed upon.

3.3 Overview of test matrix

Below in [Table I](#) is given an overview of the test matrix. More detailed tests are given in ANNEX I – First version of test matrix.

Table I - Test matrix overview

Batch	Sub-batch	Objectives	Kind of tests	Number of tests	Priority
RAM	RAM	Progressive flow increase	Refuelling with higher and higher flow	10	1
KPI	KPI	Prove project KPIs are reached	Fuel 100kg in 10 min; fuel at -30°C during 10 min; reach 300 g/s	15	1
PRO	SAE	Test SAE J2601-5 protocol in different ambient and operating conditions (check refuelling behaviour is safe and performant)	Fuel with SAE J2601-5 with various ambient temperatures, refuelling temperatures, test storage size, initial pressures and temperature, flows, ...	50	1
	SAO	Test SAE J2601-5 options and features (K0 method, volume measurement, pressure pulse) to give feedback on their accuracy to the industry	Test K0 method, PRR-Taper method, volume measurement method, ... in SAE J2601-5	15	2
	PRH	Test PRHYDE protocols to give feedback on their performance to the industry	Fuel with PRHYDE TInitial+ and PRHYDE TgasThrottle	20	2
PAR	EMT	Conduct specific tests desired by EMERSON-T to qualify their product	Check behaviour at low inlet pressure	2	1
	EMM	Conduct specific tests desired by EMERSON-M to qualify their product	Constant flow fuelling; precooled H2 into flowmeter if possible; comparison to high-flow field reference if any	14	1
	FOR	Conduct specific tests desired by FORVIA to qualify their product	Bank-switch at specific pressure / flow points	4	1
	ALF	Conduct specific tests desired by ALFA to qualify their product	Fluctuating inlet temperature; fluctuating outlet temperature setpoint; thermal inertia study	3	1
	LAU	Conduct specific tests desired by LAUDA to qualify their product	Refuelling with only one of the two evaporator: tests with "phase 2" configuration on the cooling system	11	1
EXT	TWN	Conduct twin-nozzle refuellings in the scope of the RHeaDHy – Toyota partnership	Twin-nozzle refuellings	97	2/3
	...	Conduct tests in partnership with other industrial or academic external partners	Examples (to be confirmed): refuelling of other tests benches or trucks; test of communication prototypes; test of other hoses / nozzles / receptacles; inter-lab studies; ...		
	EPN	(is currently being discussed with various potential partners)			
CER	FLM	Tests needed to obtain OIML R139 on flowmeter	Full fills, half fills, MMQ fills	9	1
OPT	COS	Understand better cost difference depending on refuelling time	Energy consumption for given fuelling time; study cost / time trade-off	25	3
	PRT	If room for optimization is seen after PRO testing, try improved refuelling protocols	Adaptation of current protocols		
	CAS	Test different cascade operating strategies to understand their impact on performance and cost	Various switch criterias, initial pressures, bank organization, ...		
OTH	VEH	Conduct refuellings that are typical of vehicles other than trucks, to gain in understanding	Mimic buses, trailers refuelling for instance	25	3
	STA	Use different refuelling station configuration or control logic to see impacts	Try direct compression or parallel refuelling if possible		
	SIM	Be able to validate specific points of simulation models	Vertical tank refuelling study, ...		
	...		<i>Other ideas arising during test campaign if any</i>		
Total tests of interest:				300	

4 Conclusion

The RHeaDHy test campaign represents a critical milestone in the development of hydrogen refuelling solutions for heavy-duty vehicles. Through a structured and comprehensive testing approach, the project plans to demonstrate the feasibility of high-flow hydrogen refuelling using the equipment developed.

The test matrix has been organized into thematic batches to address the project's key goals: validating high-flow hydrogen refuelling capabilities, characterizing custom-developed equipment, verifying KPIs, assessing protocol performance, and more generally supporting stakeholders in the hydrogen mobility industry. Safety considerations are integrated throughout the campaign, both in equipment design and operational procedures. A total of 300 tests of interest are planned, distributed across eight batches with varying priorities. High-priority batches are already well-defined, while lower-priority batches remain flexible to accommodate adjustments based on early test results and evolving partnerships. The test campaign is designed to be adaptive, with key milestones guiding its progression. This approach ensures that the campaign remains aligned with its technical objectives while adapting to the real test results and potential issues that may happen. **RHeaDHy project welcomes feedback and collaboration with external partners** from both industry and academia. Thus, dedicated test batches have been included in the campaign to accommodate joint testing initiatives.

Finally, it can be highlighted that RHeaDHy equipment is heavily instrumented, and data capitalization will be a key focus. To support scientific research and provide valuable insights to the hydrogen mobility sector, **selected datasets from the test campaign and a report summarizing key findings will be made publicly available.**

Once executed, the RHeaDHy test campaign is expected to generate valuable insights that will support the deployment of high-flow refuelling solutions for heavy-duty transport. The campaign is designed to establish a robust technical foundation, and its results are intended to serve as a reference for both industrial stakeholders and the research community.

Want to discuss or give feedback:

- [About test matrix?](#)
contact Lukas WILLMEROOTH and Dorine CROUSLÉ
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- [About RHeaDHy project in general?](#)
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ANNEX I – First version of test matrix

Batch	Sub-batch	Global Test n°	Sub-batch n°	Description / Desired Test Outcome	Tank / Tank System	Protocol	Initial Pressure [bar]	Ambient Temperature [°C]	Initial Gas Temperature [°C]	Precooling Temperature [°C]	Tank / Tank System Configuration	Stop Criteria
RAM	RAM	1	1	Progressive flow ramp-up	TSTS	Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		2	2	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		3	3	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		4	4	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		5	5	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		6	6	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		7	7	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		8	8	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		9	9	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
		10	10	Progressive flow ramp-up		Constant ramp rate	<100 bar	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full or partial	TBD
KPI	KPI	11	1	100 kg, -30°C held for ≥10 min	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		12	2	100 kg, -30°C held for ≥10 min - 2		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		13	3	100 kg, -30°C held for ≥10 min - 3		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		14	4	100 kg, -30°C held for ≥10 min - 4		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		15	5	100 kg, 10 min		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		16	6	100 kg, 10 min - 2		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		17	7	100 kg, 10 min - 3		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		18	8	100 kg, 10 min - 4		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		19	9	100 kg, 10 min - 5		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		20	10	100 kg, 10 min - 6		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	≤-30°C	Full TSTS	100% SOC
		21	11	300 g/s		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Reaching peak flow
		22	12	300 g/s - 2		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Reaching peak flow

		23	13	300 g/s - 3		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Reaching peak flow
		24	14	300 g/s - 4		Customized	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Reaching peak flow
		25	15	TBD (Test margin)		TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
PRO	SAE	26	1	Standard refuelling – 75 kg - 1	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank closed	Protocol - Table
		27	2	Standard refuelling – 75 kg - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank closed	Protocol - MC method
		28	3	Standard refuelling – 50 kg - 1		SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
		29	4	Standard refuelling – 50 kg - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - MC method
		30	5	Standard refuelling - 22 kg		SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank	Protocol - Table
		31	6	Standard refuelling - 25 kg		SAE J2601-5	50	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	The other large tank + small one	Protocol - MC method
		32	7	Lowest P_ini – 75 kg		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		33	8	P_ini = 100 bar - 75 kg		SAE J2601-5	100	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		34	9	P_ini = 250 bar – 75 kg		SAE J2601-5	200	15-20°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		35	10	High T_amb refuelling - 1		SAE J2601-5	100	>35°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		36	11	High T_amb refuelling - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	>35°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		37	12	Low T_amb refuelling - 1		SAE J2601-5	100	<0°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		38	13	Low T_amb refuelling - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	<0°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		39	14	Precooling temperature target -20°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-20°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		40	15	Precooling temperature: Hottest possible precooling - 1		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Hottest cooling	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		41	16	Precooling temperature: Hottest possible precooling - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Hottest cooling	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		42	17	Precooling temperature: Hottest possible precooling - 3		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Hottest cooling	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		43	18	Precooling temperature target: -40°C - 1		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
		44	19	Precooling temperature target: -40°C - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - MC method
		45	20	Fluctuating precooling temperature: -35°C then -25°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-35°C for 5 minutes, then -25°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
46	21	Fluctuating precooling temperature: -25°C then -35°C	SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-25°C for 5 minutes, then -35°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table			

	47	22	Fluctuating precooling temperature: -35°C then -15°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	-35°C for 5 minutes, then -15°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	48	23	Fluctuating precooling temperature: Slow oscillations -25 / -35°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Oscillations -25°C to -35°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	49	24	Fluctuating precooling temperature: Rapid oscillations -25 / -35°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Oscillations -25°C to -35°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	50	25	Fluctuating precooling temperature: Oscillations -15 / -35°C		SAE J2601-5	100	10 - 25°C	T_amb	Oscillations -15°C to -35°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	51	26	Low T_amb and -40°C precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	<5°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	52	27	Low T_amb and -20°C precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	<5°C	T_amb	-20°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	53	28	High T_amb and -40°C precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	> 30°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	54	29	High T_amb and -20°C precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	>30°C	T_amb	-20°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	55	30	Highest flow - Cold day - coldest precooling - 1		SAE J2601-5	50	<5°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	56	31	Highest flow - Cold day - coldest precooling - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	<0°C	T_amb	-40°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	57	32	Lowest flow 1 - Hot day - hottest precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	>30°C	T_amb	Hottest cooling	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	58	33	Lowest flow 2 - Hot day - hottest precooling		SAE J2601-5	100	>35°C	T_amb	Hottest cooling	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table
	59	34	SAE FM90 - 1		SAE J2601-5 FM90	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
	60	35	SAE FM90 - 2 (other TSTS size)		SAE J2601-5 FM90	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank	Protocol - Table
	61	36	SAE FM60 - 1		SAE J2601-5 FM60	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
	62	37	SAE FM60 - 2 (other TSTS size)		SAE J2601-5 FM60	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank	Protocol - Table
	63	38	SAE FM60 - 3 (cold conditions)		SAE J2601-5 FM60	100	<10°C	T_amb	-40°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
	64	39	Back-to-back 1 - 1	TSTS - Skid 1, then 2&3	SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Skid 1	Protocol - Table
	65	40	Back-to-back 1 - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Skids 2&3	Protocol - Table
	66	41	Back-to-back 2 - 1	TSTS + Separate Tank / Tank System	SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
	67	42	Back-to-back 2 - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Other tank system	Protocol - Table
	68	43	Back-to-back 3 - 1		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
	69	44	Back-to-back 3 - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Other tank / tank system	Protocol - Table
	70	45	Prepare hot soak 1	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	Lowest	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	100 bar reached in TSTS
	71	46	Hot soak 1		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	>T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table

SAO	72	47	Prepare hot soak 2		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	73	48	Hot soak 2		SAE J2601-5	200	0-30°C	>T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table	
	74	49	Cold soak 1		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - Table	
	75	50	Cold soak 2		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	One large tank closed or full	Protocol - MC method	
	76	1	PRR Taper (2)	TSTS	SAE J2601-5 with PRR Taper	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	77	2	PRR Taper (2)		SAE J2601-5 with PRR Taper	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	78	3	PRR Taper (2)		SAE J2601-5 with PRR Taper	150	<5°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	79	4	PRR Taper (2)		SAE J2601-5 with PRR Taper	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-40°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	80	5	PRR Taper (2)		SAE J2601-5 with PRR Taper	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-40°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	81	6	K0 Method - High flow -30°C		SAE -5 with K0 method	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	82	7	K0 Method - High flow -20°C		SAE -5 with K0 method	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-20°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method	
	83	8	K0 Method FM90 -30°C		SAE -5 FM90 with K0 method	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - MC method	
	84	9	K0 Method +non-com fuelling high-flow -30°C		SAE -5 non com with K0 method	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - MC method - Use of MP calc via K0	
	85	10	Volume measurement method - Volume 1 - P_ini = 50 bar		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	86	11	Volume measurement method - Volume 1 - P_ini = 150 bar		SAE J2601-5	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	87	12	Volume measurement method - Volume 2 - P_ini = 100 bar, T_amb cold		SAE J2601-5	100	<5°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	88	13	Volume measurement method - Volume 2 - P_ini = 100 bar, T_amb hot		SAE J2601-5	100	> 30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	89	14	Volume measurement method - Volume 3 - P_ini = 50 bar		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	90	15	Volume measurement method - Volume 5 - 100 kg P_ini = 150 bar		SAE J2601-5	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	200 bar reached in TSTS	
	PRH	91	1	Volume measurement method - Volume 5 - 100 kg P_ini = 150 bar	TSTS	PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol
		92	2	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini - 30°C		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol

² If performance if not good at first in PRO-SAE batch (too much pressure drop), we will use PRR Taper all the time in the previous batch and switch these tests into "non PRR Taper tests"

		93	3	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - High P_ini - Normal T_ini - 30°C		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		94	4	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini - 40°C		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-40°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		95	5	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini - 20°C		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-20°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		96	6	Prepare hot soak		SAE J2601-5	Lowest	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	150 bar reached in TSTS		
		97	7	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Hot soak		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	150	0-30°C	>T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		98	8	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Low P_ini - Cold soak		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	50	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		99	9	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Cold soak		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	100	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		100	10	Tgasini+ - Full TSTS - High P_ini - Cold soak		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	150	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		101	11	Tgasini+ - Half TSTS - Low P_ini - Normal T_ini		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		102	12	Tgasini+ - Half TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		103	13	Tgasini+ - Half TSTS - High P_ini - Normal T_ini		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	150	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		104	14	Tgasini+ - Half TSTS - Low P_ini - Cold soak		PRHYDE - TgasInitial+	50	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		105	15	Tgasini+ - Half TSTS - High P_ini - Cold soak		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle	150	0-30°C	<T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		106	16	TgasThrottle - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini -30°C		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		107	17	TgasThrottle - Full TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini -30°C - hot day		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle	100	>30°	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		108	18	TgasThrottle - Change default throttle if relevant given previous results		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle (adapted if relevant)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		109	19	TgasThrottle - Change default throttle if relevant given previous results		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle (adapted if relevant)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol		
		110	20	TgasThrottle - Half TSTS - Med P_ini - Normal T_ini -30°C		PRHYDE - TgasThrottle	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol		
		PAR	EMT	111	1	EM-T tests with specific setup - 1	TSTS	Customized	Lowest	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
				112	2	EM-T tests with specific setup - 2	TSTS	Customized	Lowest	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
EMM	113		1	Constant flow period - 1	TSTS	Customized	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	TBC	100% SOC		
	114		2	Constant flow period - 2	TSTS	Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	TBC	100% SOC		
	115		3	Constant flow period - 3	TSTS	Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	TBC	100% SOC		
116	4	Constant flow period - 4	TSTS	Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	TBC	100% SOC				
117	5	Lowest flow possible - 1	TSTS	Customized	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC				

		118	6	Lowest flow possible - 2		Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
		119	7	Lowest flow possible - 3		Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
		120	8	Lowest flow possible - 4		Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
		121	9	Lowest flow possible - 4 (repeat)		Customized (adapted based previous results)	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC
		122	10	EM-M tests with specific setup - 1		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		123	11	EM-M tests with specific setup - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		124	12	EM-M tests with specific setup - 3		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		125	13	EM-M tests with specific setup - 4		SAE J2601-5	100	TBD	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
		126	14	EM-M tests with specific setup - 5		SAE J2601-5	100	TBD	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table
	FOR	127	1	Forvia tests with specific setup - 1	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		128	2	Forvia tests with specific setup - 2		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		129	3	Forvia tests with specific setup - 3		SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		130	4	Forvia tests with specific setup - 4		SAE J2601	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
	ALF	131	1	Alfa Laval tests with specific setup - 1	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
132		2	Alfa Laval tests with specific setup - 2	SAE J2601-5		100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table	
133		3	Alfa Laval tests with specific setup - 3	SAE J2601-5		100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table	
LAU	134	1	2nd cooling system setup - Standard refuelling – 75 kg - 1	TSTS	SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank (closed)	Protocol - Table	
	135	2	2nd cooling system setup - Standard refuelling – 75 kg - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank (closed)	Protocol - Table	
	136	3	2nd cooling system setup - Standard refuelling – 75 kg - 3		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Single large tank (closed)	Protocol - Table	
	137	4	2nd cooling system setup - Partial refuelling - 1		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table	
	138	5	2nd cooling system setup - Partial refuelling - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table	
	139	6	2nd cooling system setup - Partial refuelling - 3		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	Protocol - Table	
	140	7	2nd cooling system setup - Low flow refuelling - 1		Customized	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC	
	141	8	2nd cooling system setup - Low flow refuelling - 2		Customized	100	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	One skid only	100% SOC	
	142	9	Cold ambient start-up and use of cooling unie		SAE J2601-5	100	<0°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table	

		143	10	Additional Lauda tests with specific setup - 1		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
		144	11	Additional Lauda tests with specific setup - 2		SAE J2601-5	50	0-30°C	T_amb	-30°C	Full TSTS	Protocol - Table
EXT	TWN	145	1	Is being determined with Toyota	Toyota Tank System	Twin Nozzle	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD	TBD
		
		
	EP2 to EPN	Sub-batches for external partnerships currently under discussion or room for additional external partners
		
		184	
CER	FLM	242	1	OIML-certification testing with notified body	
			
		250	9			
OPT	COST	251	1	To be specified after priority batches are done	
			
			
	PRT	...	1			
			
			
CAS	...	1				
				
				
OTH	VEH	...	1	To be specified after priority batches are done	
			
			
	STA	...	1			
			
			
SIM	...	1			

			...										
			...										
	TBD		1										
		300	...										

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